

Practice Abstract no. 27

Food and nutrition components - Food nutrition information

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the food nutrition information component, particularly its characteristics, specific formats, functionalities, the mechanisms in which they operate, and the licensing terms under which it can be made available.

What is provided	An application that automatically retrieves product information from free online product databases given a food's name.
Component format	A <i>.py</i> (Python) script.
What it does	Automatically extracts food information such as nutrients, kcal, and other characteristics of a food from free online databases (e.g., the USDA).
How it works	Given a food's name (e.g., apple, rice, etc.), the application automatically connects to the open-source online databases (e.g., the USDA) via the corresponding API, and retrieves the corresponding food information.
Technical details/considerations	The requirements of this component are: Python 3.6, pip version 23.1.2, request library version 23.1.2.
Related datasets/standards	In the provided implementation, the component connects to the USDA ¹ dataset of food products, which is based on free contributions by the USA government.
References	https://fdc.nal.usda.gov
IPR considerations	The component is provided under the following licence: "Food nutrition information" © 2024 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL) , Information Technologies Institute (ITI) , Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is marked with CC0 1.0 .

¹ <https://fdc.nal.usda.gov>


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Food Name: APPLE
Nutritional Information (per 100g):
  Calcium, Ca: 0.0 MG
  Iron, Fe: 0.23 MG
  Sodium, Na: 0.0 MG
  Vitamin A, IU: 65.0 IU
  Vitamin C, total ascorbic acid: 3.1 MG
  Cholesterol: 0.0 MG
  Fatty acids, total saturated: 0.0 G
  Protein: 0.0 G
  Carbohydrate, by difference: 14.3 G
  Energy: 52.0 KCAL
  Total Sugars: 10.4 G
  Fiber, total dietary: 3.2 G
  Potassium, K: 110 MG
  Fatty acids, total trans: 0.0 G
  Total lipid (fat): 0.65 G
```

Example of the Food nutrition information script output for the food apple

